

(WAI). This is distinct from the usual tungro symptoms of stunting, yellow or yellow-orange discoloration, and reduced tillering observed in susceptible populations of other species.

Fifty 11-d-old seedlings of each accession were inoculated with 10 viruliferous green leafhopper (GLH) adults/seedling for 4 h. We caged another 10 seedlings of each accession with 10

virus-free GLH adults/seedling for 4 h to check whether necrosis resulted from sucking damage by GLH alone.

Seedlings inoculated with viruliferous GLH first showed necrosis at the leaf tips 2 WAI. Necrosis advanced systemically through the seedlings; few survived beyond 3 WAI. Seedlings caged with virus-free GLH did not show any necrosis. Therefore, tungro viruses

caused the necrosis, which is the most severe reaction to tungro we have observed.

We have systematically been screening wild relatives of rice for tungro resistance and have also found systemic necrosis in *O. barthii*, the close wild relative of *O. glaberrima*. This severe systemic necrosis may be species specific. □

Resistance to rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) found in wild *Oryza* spp.

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We evaluated wild relatives of rice to seek new resistance genes for use in the control of tungro. A partial core collection of 156 accessions, representing the genetic diversity in the genus *Oryza*, was used (Table 1).

Eleven-day-old seedlings were inoculated with viruliferous green leafhopper (GLH) adults at 10 insects/plant for 4 h. Leaves were individually sampled 2-3 wk after inoculation to test for RTBW and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) infection by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Ten of the 12 accessions, which were not infected with RTBV, were tested for antibiosis to GLH (Table 2). Either a 10-d-old seedling or a leaf tip of an adult plant from each accession was placed in a test tube with five GLH nymphs (2d instar). This was replicated 10 times. We graded antibiosis of each accession as high, moderate, or low by counting the surviving GLH nymphs each day for 3 d. The accessions resistant to any virus were determined from the data of more than 10 plants.

In the *O. sativa* complex, *O. nivara* and natural hybrids were resistant to RTSV; but no accession in *O. sativa* complex was resistant to RTBV infection.

The accessions, which were not infected with RTBV, showed a low infection rate with RTSV, except *O.*

longiglumis (IRGC 105146) (Table 2). *O. brachyantha* (IRGC 100115), *O. officinalis* (IRGC 105100, IRGC 105365), and *O. rhizomatis* (IRGC 103421) were not infected by either RTBV or RTSV.

The accessions resistant to RTRV infection showed a high level of antibiosis to GLH. Thus it is difficult to distinguish the resistance to virus infection from the resistance to the vector.

Table 1. Screening wild rices for tungro resistance.

Species	Genome	Tested	Accessions (no.)		
			RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	FF	5	1	0	4
<i>O. sativa</i> complex					
<i>O. nivara</i>	AA	39	0	0	4
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	AA	6	0	0	0
Natural hybrids	AA	25	0	0	3
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	AA	4	0	0	0
<i>O. barthii</i>	AA	6	0	0	0
<i>A. meridionalis</i>	AA	2	0	0	0
<i>O. ridleyi</i> complex					
<i>O. longiglumis</i>	Tetraploid	3	0	1	0
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	Tetraploid	5	0	2	0
<i>O. officinalis</i> complex					
<i>O. officinalis</i>	CC	14	2	2	3
<i>O. rhizomatis</i>	CC	6	1	0	0
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	CC	5	0	0	2
<i>O. malampuzhaensis</i>	BBCC	3	0	0	1
<i>O. minuta</i>	BRCC	12	0	0	5
<i>O. punctata</i>	BB, BBCC	7	0	0	2
<i>O. latifolia</i>	CCDD	5	0	1	1
<i>O. alta</i>	CCDD	3	0	2	0
<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	CCDD	2	0	0	0
<i>O. australiensis</i>	EE	4	0	0	2

Table 2. Reaction of RTBV-resistant wild rices to RTSV infection and antibiosis.

Species	IRGC acc. no.	Origin	Plants tested (no.)	Infected with RTSV (%)	Antibiosis to GLH ^b
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	100115	Guinea	29	0	11
<i>O. longiglumis</i>	105146	Indonesia	24	33	11
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	100821	Unknown	11	9	11
<i>O. officinalis</i>	101453	Malaysia	30	3	—
	104672	Malaysia	20	5	H
	105100	Brunei	28	0	H
	105365	Thailand	41	0	H
<i>O. rhizomatis</i>	105376	Thailand	29	3	M
	103421	Sri Lanka	18	0	—
<i>O. latifolia</i>	105139	Guatemala	25	4	H
<i>O. alta</i>	100967	Surinam	19	10	H
	105685	Brazil	29	11	H

^aH = high level of antibiosis, M = moderate level of antibiosis.

Wide hybridization between rice and most of its wild relatives is now possible. Genes for insect resistance from *O.*

officinalis have been successfully incorporated into advanced breeding lines. Therefore, the various sources of

resistance reported are potential donors for resistance to the tungro viruses. □

Performance of a bacterial blight (BB)-resistant rice variety in the endemic pockets of Konkan Region, India

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Karjat 1 (Holamaldiga/IR36) is an early-maturing rice with high resistance to BB at both the vegetative phase and flower-

ing stage. The variety, released by KKV, is specifically for the BB-endemic areas of Konkan Region (west coast).

The variety and susceptible checks EK70 (local) and Karjat 184 were tested during the five kharif (monsoon) seasons of 1985-86 to 1989-90, in farmers' fields. We recorded BB incidence three times using the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)* 0-9 scale.

At vegetative phase, Karjat 1 was free of BB as foliar and kressek infec-

tions during all years studied (see table). Average incidence of BB at flowering and grain filling ranged from 0.12 to 1.24, with a maximum of 0.4 at flowering stage and 1.5 at grain filling. Average incidence of BB was 3.90-6.72 on Karjat 184 and 3.92-7.22 on EK70.

Karjat 184 had an average kressek infection of 3.54 and EK70, 3.64.

The study indicates that farmers can adopt Karjat 1 for cultivation in BB-endemic areas of Konkan Region. □

Performance of Karjat 1, Karjat 184, and EK70 in BB endemic areas in Konkan Region, India, 1985-86 to 1989-90.

Year	Locations (no.)	Av BB incidence ^a												
		Vegetative ^b				BB at flowering			BB at grain filling			Av grain yield (t/ha)		
		Karjat 184		EK70		Karjat I	Karjat 184	EK70	Karjat I	Karjat 184	EK70	Karjat I	Karjat 184	EK70
		BB	Kressek	BB	Kressek									
1985-86	5	0.0	0.1	1.4	2.4	0.4	2.4	6.2	1.0	4.6	7.2	4.2	3.9	2.8
1986-87	5	7.7	7.0	5.0	4.4	0.1	6.2	5.2	1.2	6.5	5.4	3.6	1.6	2.6
1987-88	4	5.0	2.4	5.0	3.0	0.1	7.2	7.0	1.5	9.0	8.0	4.1	2.8	2.8
1988-89	2	2.4	2.0	3.2	2.4	0.0	4.6	4.9	1.0	6.2	6.5	3.7	3.0	2.9
1989-90	6	4.4	6.2	5.0	6.0	0.0	5.6	5.6	1.5	7.3	9.0	3.2	2.0	1.8
Av		3.00	3.54	3.92	3.64	0.12	5.16	5.78	1.24	6.72	7.22	3.8	2.7	2.6

^a 1976 SES scale for BB: 0 = no BB incidence. 9 = 5 100% area of upper 3 leaves showing necrotic symptoms. SES scale for kressek: 0 = no incidence. 9 = 91-100% hills affected. ^b Karjat 1 had no BB at vegetative phase.

Pest resistance—insects

Insecticide-induced resurgence of brown planthopper (BPH) on IR62

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Many farmers in Koronadal, Philippines, apply sprays of synthetic pyrethroids to their rice as early as 1-2 wk after transplanting (WT) regardless of numbers of insect pests or beneficial arthropods. These sprays are perceived as "insur-

ance"—even when varieties have insect resistance. Resurgence of BPH populations on susceptible varieties due to the destruction of natural enemies is well documented. Little information is available, however, on the impact of these chemical sprays on BPH and natural enemy populations on resistant rice varieties.

We established a trial in a farmer's field in Caloocan, Koronadal, during the 1986 wet season (Jul-Sep) to demonstrate the effects of broad-spectrum chemical applications on BPH and spiders (major BPH predators) on resistant variety IR62. An area of 800 m² was planted and divided into two equal parts. One part was sprayed at 10 days after transplanting (DT) with a synthetic pyrethroid

BPH and spiders (no./20 hills)

Total number of BPH and spiders sampled by D-vac. Caloocan, South Cotabato, Philippines, 1986 wet season.